

EFFECT OF INM AND PLANT GEOMETRY ON YIELD OF RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.) VARIETIES UNDER SRI TECHNIQUE.Harikesh^{1*}, Akhtar Ali¹ and Dileep Kumar Tiwari²¹Department of Agronomy, ²Department of Horticulture,

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(MS Received: 03.02.2024; MS Revised:04.03.2024; MS Accepted:05.03.2024)

MS 3185

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRONOMY,)

Abstract

The present investigation was carried out at Agronomy Research Farm of Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture & Technology, Narendra Nagar (Kumarganj), Ayodhya (U.P.) during Kharif seasons of 2015 and 2016 to study the "Effect of integrated nutrient management and plant geometry on productivity of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) Varieties under SRI technique". The experiment consisting 24 combinations of 6 levels INM [F₀: Control, F₁: RDF (120:60:60), F₂: 50% RDF + 50% N through vermicompost, F₃: 75% RDF + 25% N through vermicompost, F₄: 50% RDF + 50% N through FYM, F₅: 75% RDF + 25% N through FYM], plant geometry (S₁: 20 cm × 20 cm and S₂: 30 cm × 30 cm) and varieties (V₁-NDR-359 and V₂- Sarju 52). The experiments were conducted in Factorial Randomized Block Design (R.B.D.) with three replications. The application INM treatment F₂ (50 % RDF + 50%N through vermicompost), varieties (NDR-359) and plant geometry (20 cm × 20 cm) were recorded significantly yield ($q\ ha^{-1}$) (grain and straw) which was statistically at par with INM treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + N through FYM) during both the years and in pooled analysis.

The interaction effects of INM treatments and plant geometry were found significant for grain yield and straw yield ($q\ ha^{-1}$) during both the years and in pooled analysis. Grain and straw yield ($q\ ha^{-1}$) were recorded in INM treatment F₂: 50% RDF + 50% N through vermicompost in combination with S₁: 20 cm × 20 cm during both the years and in pooled analysis. Thus it may be concluded that INM treatment F₂ in combination with variety NDR-359 and plant geometry 20 cm × 20 cm proved as the most suitable practice.

Keywords: SRI, Yield, Farm yard manure, Vermicompost.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a member of poaceae family chromosome number 24 (2n) and most important staple food crop for millions of mankind from dawn of civilization. Among the cereal crops, it serves as the principal source of nourishment for over half of the global population.

Total production of Rice during 2019-2020 is estimated at record 117.94 million tonnes. It is higher by 8.17 million tonnes than the five years average production of 109.77 million tonnes (P.I.B. Delhi.,2020). Uttar Pradesh is an important rice growing state in the country. The area and production of rice in this state is about 5.91 million hectares and production 15.56 million tonnes with an average productivity of 2.63 tonnes per hectare, respectively (P.I.B.,2022).

The system of Rice Intensification (SRI) was developed by a Jesuit agriculturist Fr. Henri De Laulanie (1993) and Madagascar colleagues working with him in 1980 and the 1990, and they studied ways to increase the low yields of Madagascar farmers. From Madagascar's poor soils which yielded usually an average of 2 tones per hectare. SRI system coaxed yield of 6, 8 and even 10 tonnes per hectare, while reducing the farmers' cost for water, seeds and external inputs. In 1990, Fr. De Laulanie and his colleagues set up an NGO called Association TefySaina ('to improve the mind') to develop SRI further and to promote it among Madagascar farmers.

Rajesh *et al.* (2003) reported that seedling planted at wider spacing of 30 x 30 cm got sufficient space to grow and also utilised resource in a better way. Therefore, younger seedlings planted at wider spacing was congenial for higher yield of both hybrid (PHB- 71) and non – hybrid (NDR- 359) rice cultivation.

In association with this most of the scientist concluded that 50% organic sources and 50% from inorganic sources and 50% from inorganic sources is the best combination in rice based cropping system to improve soil physico-chemical properties, yield and nutrient uptake capacity of rice (Wolie and Admassu, 2016 and Sharma, 2013).

Materials And Methods**Study Site**

The field experiment was conducted during Kharif 2015 and 2016 at Agronomy Farm of Acharya Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Narendra Nagar (Kumarganj), Faizabad (U.P.). The experimental site located at Kumarganj is situated 42 km

away from Faizabad city on Faizabad- Raibarely road. Geographically the experimental site is situated at 26.47° North latitude and 81.12° East longitude with is an elevation of about 113 m. from mean sea level in the Indo Gangatic Plain Zone of eastern Uttar Pradesh.

The climate in this region is humid and characterized with high rainfall (300 cm year⁻¹). The soil is sandy to sandy loam with a pH of 5.05 and 0.72% organic C. Soil low in available N (127.92 kg ha⁻¹), medium in available P (21.59 kg ha⁻¹) and low in available K (122.46 kg ha⁻¹).

Experimental Set up**Field Layout**

The treatment was carried out with 24 treatment combination formed with six nutrient management levels, two varieties and two levels of plant geometry, in rice which were allocated in Factorial Randomized Block Design with 3 replications. Each replication was separated by 1m alley, while each plot was separated by 0.5m bund space. The individual plot size was 18 m with 6 m length and 3 m breadth. The plant geometry was 20 cm×20 cm. row to row and plant to plant distance maintaining 15 row with 30 hills per row in each plot. and 30 cm × 30 cm, row to row and plant to plant distance maintaining 10 row with 20 hills per row in each plot. The central eleven rows were considered as net plot rows for yield calculation and taking observations. Two rows on each side of net plot rows were used to take destructive sample for growth analysis. The remaining two rows on each side of destructive rows were considered as border row.

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Table 1. Effect of INM and plant geometry on rice under SRI technique randomly allocated at different study plots, Kumarganj, Ayodhya, U.P.

Treatments	combination of fertilizers
F ₀	Control
F ₁	RDF (120:60:60)
F ₂	50% RDF + 50% N-Vermicompost
F ₃	75% RDF + 25% N-Vermicompost
F ₄	50% RDF + 50% N-FYM
F ₅	75% RDF + 25% N- FYM

RDF = Recommended does of fertilizer; N- Vermicompost = Nitrogen through vermicompost, N- FYM= Nitrogen through Farmyard manure

Treatment detail

Treatment combination: 24

Replication: 3

Plot size: 6 m × 3 m

Spacing: S₁ = 20 cm × 20 cm. and S₂ = 30 cm × 30 cm

distance between plant to plant and line to line i-e square planting

Rice varieties: V₁-NDR-359 and V₂- Sarju 52

Cultivation Practices Adapted

Nursery beds were prepared at small plot. A common procedure was followed in raising seedlings in the seedbed. The seedbed was prepared by puddling with repeated ploughing followed by laddering. Weeds were removed and irrigation was gently provided to the bed as and when necessary. The sprouted seeds were broadcasted in seedbed on 01.07.2015 and 05.07.2016. The moisture was maintained in the seedbed properly at two to three day interval, which ensured proper growth of all the seedlings in the seedbed. The seed rate for 20 × 20 cm was 6 kg/ha and for 30 × 30 cm was 4 kg/ha.

After the harvest of previous crop the experimental field was ploughed once with soil turning plough and cross harrowed two times. After each ploughing, planking was done to level the field and obtain the fine tilth and lay out was done.

The specific quantity of each fertilizer was calculated on the basis of gross plot size and as per treatment taken per plot. The optimum dose of fertilizers 120:60:60 was calculated for rice. The half quantity of nitrogen and full quantity of phosphorus and potassium were broadcasted in the field during final field preparation as basal dose before the transplanting in the field. The rest half dose of nitrogen was top-dressed in two splits dose after first and second irrigation at 45 DAT and 75 DAT. The crop was fertilised with an uniform dose of 60 kg P₂O₅/ha through single super phosphate, 60 kg K₂O/ha through muriate of potash and half dose of the Nitrogen management as per treatments with organic and inorganic. Two hand weeding were done with 'kharpi' at 20 and 40 days after transplanting.

12 to 14 days old seedlings were transplanted in the prepared plot just after uprooting from the nursery bed and this process completed within two to four hours. Only one seedling was planted per hill in square pattern 20 × 20 (S₁) and 30 × 30 (S₂) cm spacing on date 14.07.2015 and 18.07.2016. During the year of experimentation, there were occurrence of sufficient rains during vegetative stage, however there was occasional moisture stress during reproductive phase, hence four irrigations were given at different stages viz., 10 DAT, flowering and milking stages and grain filling stage of crop growth. The crop was harvested manually by serrated edged sickles at physiological maturity when panicle had about 85% ripened spikelet and upper portion of spikelet's look straw coloured. At the time of harvesting the grains were subjected to hard enough, having less than 16 percent moisture in the grains. First of all, the border area was harvested. The harvesting of net plot area was done separately and the harvested material from each net plot was carefully bundled and tagged after drying for three days in the field and then brought to the threshing floor. The bundle of harvested produce of each net plot was weighed after sun drying for recording biological yield. Threshing of each bundle of individual plot was done manually by wooden sticks.

The grain yield of individual plot after winnowing was weighed. The quantity of straw per plot was calculated by subtracting the weight of grains from biological produce. Yield of both grain and straw was expressed in q ha⁻¹.

Observations recorded

Yield

Grain yield (q ha⁻¹)

After taking the weight of total biomass, the producer of each net plot was threshed separated and clean grains were sun dried to maintain 12-14% moisture. The grain yield was recorded in kg plot⁻¹ and finally the values were converted into q ha⁻¹.

Straw yield (q ha⁻¹)

Straw yield from net plot area was computed by subtracting the grain yield from total produce harvested and later on converted into qha⁻¹.

Harvest index (%)

Harvest index is the ratio between the economic yield and biological yield and calculated by formula as given by Donald (1976). It was expressed in percentage.

$$\text{Harvest index} = \frac{\text{Economic yield}}{\text{Biological yield}} \times 100$$

Where, The Biological yield = Grain yield + Straw yield

Results

Grain Yield (q ha⁻¹)

In SRI technique the data on grain yield was significantly influenced due to various INM treatments, varieties and plant geometry during Y₁ (2015), Y₂ (2016) and over seasons (pooled) have been presented in Table 2 and depicted in Fig. 1.

In 2015, the maximum grain yield (57.66 q ha⁻¹) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost), which was significantly higher than INM treatments F₀ (control), F₁-RDF(120:60:60), F₅(75% RDF + 25% N through FYM) and F₃ (75% RDF + 25% N through vermicompost). It was statistically at par with treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). However, the minimum grain yield (27.97 q ha⁻¹) was recorded in F₀ (control). Variety NDR-359 recorded maximum grain yield (48.91 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than Sarju-52. The plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum grain yield (52.34 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than S₂ (30cm×30cm).

In 2016, the maximum grain yield (59.23) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) which, was significantly higher than F₀ (control), F₁-RDF(120:60:60), F₅ (75% RDF + 25% N through FYM) and F₃ (75% RDF + 25% N through vermicompost) except treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). It was statistically at par with (56.35 q ha⁻¹) F₄. However, the lowest grain yield (28.74 q ha⁻¹) was recorded INM treatment in F₀ (control). Among variety NDR-359 recorded maximum grain yield (50.24 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than Sarju-52. The plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum grain yield (53.76 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than S₂ (30cm×30cm).

In pooled analysis, the maximum grain yield (58.45) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through

vermicompost) which, was significantly higher than rest of other INM treatments except treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). It was statistically at par with F₄. However, the minimum grain yield (28.36 q ha⁻¹) was recorded in F₀ (control). Variety NDR-359 produced maximum grain yield (49.57 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than Sarju-52. The plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded highest grain yield (53.05 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than S₂ (30cm×30cm).

Interaction effects

The interaction effects between INM treatments and plant geometry were found significant for grain yield during both the year and pooled analysis under SRI technique. The maximum grain yield was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) in combination with plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) (59.48, 61.10 and 60.29) during both the years and pooled analysis, respectively (Table 3).

Straw yield (q ha⁻¹)

The straw yield was significantly influenced due to different INM treatments, varieties and plant geometry under SRI technique during Y₁ (2015), Y₂ (2016 q ha⁻¹) and over seasons (pooled) have been presented in Table 2 and depicted in Fig. 2.

In 2015, the maximum straw yield (79.26 q ha⁻¹) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost), which was significantly higher than rest of other INM treatments except treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). It was statistically at par with F₄. However, the minimum straw yield (42.23 q ha⁻¹) was observed in F₀ (control). Variety Sarju-52 produced maximum straw yield (73.88 q ha⁻¹), which was significantly higher than NDR-359 under SRI technique. The plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum straw yield (73.98 q ha⁻¹), which was significantly higher than S₂ (30 cm × 30 cm).

In 2016, the maximum straw yield (83.70 q ha⁻¹) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost), which was significantly higher than rest of the INM treatments except treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). It was statistically at par with F₄. However, the minimum straw yield (43.57 q ha⁻¹) was observed in F₀ (control) under SRI technique. Variety Sarju-52 produced maximum straw yield (78.05 q ha⁻¹), which was significantly higher than NDR-359. The plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum straw yield in pooled (77.79 q ha⁻¹), which was significantly higher than S₂ (30cm×30cm).

In pooled analysis, the maximum straw yield (81.48 q ha⁻¹) was recorded with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) which was significantly higher than rest of the INM treatments except treatment F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). It was statistically at par with F₄. However, the minimum straw yield (42.90 q ha⁻¹) was observed in F₀ (control) under SRI technique. Variety Sarju-52 recorded maximum straw yield (75.96 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than NDR-359. Under SRI technique the plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum straw yield (75.89 q ha⁻¹) which, was significantly higher than S₂ (30 cm × 30 cm).

Harvest Index (%)

The data on harvest index was not significantly influenced due to various integrated nutrient management, varieties and plant geometry have been presented in Table 4.9 Data indicated that INM treatments were not significantly effected on the harvest index. Highest harvest index was found with the application of INM treatments F₂-50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost (42.22, 41.22 and 41.72%) during both the year and pooled analysis, respectively under SRI technique. However, lowest harvest index was observed with F₅ (39.75, 38.78 and 39.27%) during both the years, respectively. Among varieties NDR-359 recorded maximum straw yield (40.41, 39.62 and 40.01%) during both the year and pooled analysis, respectively under SRI technique which, was significantly higher than Sarju-52. Under SRI technique the plant geometry S₁ (20 cm × 20 cm) recorded maximum harvest index (41.38, 40.57 and 40.98%)

during both the year and pooled analysis, respectively under SRI technique which, was significantly higher than S₂ (30 cm × 30 cm).

Discussion

Effect of Integrated Nutrient Management treatments

Yield is the result of coordinated inter play of growth characters and yield attributes. Grain and straw yield were significantly influenced by the different nutrient management. Highest grain yield was recorded with INM treatment of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) followed by F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). The maximum improvement of yield 25.53% with the application of F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) followed by 19.41 % with the application of F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM), 13.29 with the application F₃ and 8.35% with the application of F₅ (75% RDF+25 % N- through FYM) over F₁ (RDF-120:60:60) in pooled analysis. This might be due to adequate nutrient availability, which contributed to better growth parameters and yield attributes. Productivity of crop collectively determined by vigor of the vegetative growth and yield attributes. Better vegetative growth coupled with higher yield attributes resulted in higher grain and straw yields. Lowest grain yield was recorded under F₀ (control) due to poor nutrient supply during the period of growth. Poor nutrient supply during the critical stages reduced the yield attributes and resulted in poor grain and straw yields during 2015 and 2016. The similar results were reported by Gupta & Singh (1992), Das *et al.*, (2002), Raju and Devi (2005), Zaidi *et al.* (2006) and Sujata *et al.* (2014).

Harvest index is a function of grain and straw yield. Highest harvest index was noted under F₂ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through vermicompost) followed by F₄ (50 % RDF + 50 % N through FYM). But harvest index was not significantly influenced by different nutrient levels during both of the years. This might be due to the fact that adequate nutrient under the higher nutrient availability increased the grain yield than that of biological yield obtained by Bhat *et al* (2005).

Effect of variety

The grain yield was significantly higher in cultivar NDR-359 which was statistically comparable with cultivar Sarju-52 (Table 2). In comparison to NDR-359, sarju-52 which might have increased in panicle bearing shoots m⁻² as well as number of grains per panicle and 1000-grain weight. The statistically comparable grain yield in NDR-359 and Sarju-52 was due to higher number of effective tillers m⁻² in cultivar NDR-359 and higher values of yield attributing characters in cultivar NDR-359.

Variations in straw yield due to cultivars were in decreasing order (Table 2). Cultivar sarju-52 recorded significantly low straw yield as compared to NDR-359 cultivar. The significantly less straw yield in cultivar Sarju-52 might be due to lesser dry matter accumulation the present findings are in conformity of Dey *et al.* (2006).

The harvest index was significantly higher in cultivar NDR-359 than the rest of the tested cultivars (Table 2) which might be due to less straw yield obtained and higher grain yield demonstrating better dry matter. But in case of NDR-359 as a medium duration crop (142.22 days) its straw yield was more, thus harvest index of Sarju-52 is significantly lower than the NDR-359.

Effect of Plant Geometry

Plant Geometry is one of the important factors to obtain higher grain yield in rice cultivars under SRI technique. Optimum plant spacing depends on several factors such as the plant type, season, fertility level and date of seeding.

The higher yield in plant spacing (20 cm x20 cm) might be due to higher growth in case of plant height, number of shoot that increases the biological production. Variations in harvest index due to plant spacing were non significant (Table 2) Limochi, (2012).

Conclusion

The observations were recorded on yield parameters in SRI technique the yield (grain and straw) were influenced significantly due to various INM treatments, varieties and plant geometry during both the

year and pooled analysis. The maximum grain yield and straw yield 7.0 qha^{-1} was recorded in treatment 50% RDF + 50% N through vermicompost, variety NDR-359 and plant geometry 20 cm × 20 cm during both the year and in pooled analysis.

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Table 2: Effect of integrated nutrient management, varieties and plant geometry on yield of rice under SRI technique.

Treatment	Grain yield (qha ⁻¹)			Straw yield (qha ⁻¹)			Harvest index (%)		
	2015	2016	Pooled	2015	2016	Pooled	2015	2016	Pooled
Integrated Nutrients Management									
F ₀	27.97	28.74	28.36	42.23	43.57	42.90	39.82	39.40	39.61
F ₁	45.93	47.18	46.56	74.63	78.82	76.72	37.91	36.96	37.44
F ₂	57.66	59.23	58.45	79.26	83.70	81.48	42.22	41.22	41.72
F ₃	52.05	53.46	52.75	79.10	83.60	81.33	39.56	38.59	39.07
F ₄	54.85	56.35	55.60	78.88	83.32	81.10	40.95	39.96	40.46
F ₅	49.77	51.12	50.45	75.09	79.30	77.19	39.75	38.78	39.27
SEm₊	0.95	0.98	0.68	1.35	1.49	0.98	0.65	0.65	0.46
CD at 5%	2.72	2.79	1.92	3.85	4.06	2.76	NS	NS	NS
Varieties									
V ₁	48.91	50.24	49.57	69.19	72.71	70.95	40.41	39.62	40.01
V ₂	47.17	48.46	47.82	73.88	78.05	75.96	39.67	38.68	39.18
SEm₊	0.55	0.57	0.39	0.78	0.82	0.57	0.38	0.37	0.27
CD at 5%	1.57	1.61	1.11	2.22	2.34	1.59	NS	NS	NS
Plan geometry									
S ₁	52.34	53.76	53.05	73.98	77.79	75.89	41.38	40.57	40.98
S ₂	43.74	43.74	44.34	69.08	72.96	71.02	38.69	37.73	38.21
SEm₊	0.55	0.57	0.39	0.78	0.82	0.57	0.38	0.37	0.27
CD at 5%	1.57	1.61	1.11	2.22	2.34	1.59	NS	NS	NS

Table 3: Interaction effect of plant geometry and INM on grain yield (q ha⁻¹)

Integrated Nutrient management	Plant geometry								
	2015			2016			Pooled		
	S ₁	S ₂	Mean	S ₁	S ₂	mean	S ₁	S ₂	mean
F ₀	31.83	24.12	27.97	32.69	24.78	28.74	32.26	24.45	28.36
F ₁	52.87	38.99	45.93	54.31	40.06	47.18	53.59	39.52	46.56
F ₂	59.48	55.85	57.66	61.10	57.37	59.23	60.29	56.61	58.45
F ₃	56.84	47.25	52.05	58.39	48.54	53.46	57.61	47.90	52.75
F ₄	58.82	50.89	54.85	60.42	52.28	56.35	59.62	51.58	55.60
F ₅	54.19	45.34	49.77	55.67	46.58	51.12	54.93	45.96	50.45
Mean	52.34	43.74		53.76	44.93		53.05	44.34	
NXS	SEm_± = 1.35			SEm_± = 1.39			SEm_± = 1.37		
	CD at 5% = 3.84			CD at 5% = 3.95			CD at 5% = 3.84		